

The Limits of Scientific Progress

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Abstract

The notion that science invariably advances is questioned, arguing that the current era of rapid scientific progress could constitute a temporary anomaly. Furthermore, the text explores the limits of experimentation, highlighting the increasing complexity of current theories and the need for advanced technology to perform experiments, and reflects on the limited capacity of the human mind to understand and contribute to increasingly specialized scientific fields.

Introduction

Will our theories of the cosmos seem as wrong to our descendants as Aristotle's theories seem to us? This is the question John Horgan [1] asks his history of science students at Stevens Institute of Technology. If we analyze this question from the perspective that science and our understanding of the world are constantly advancing and growing, we would be inclined to think that our current theories about the behavior of nature possess certain degrees of error and deficiencies that we are unaware of, and therefore affirm that in the future we might look with some degree of shame at the ideas and concepts that we consider valid today in understanding nature.

At first glance, we might think that there is no valid answer and that it is simply a didactic exercise with no apparent direction. However, the fascination lies in the subsequent answer John Horgan [1] offers his students in an emphatic:

“No”, because Aristotle’s theories were wrong and ours are right. The Earth orbits the Sun, not the other way around, and our world is not made of earth, water, fire, and air, but of hydrogen, carbon, and other elements that are in turn made of quarks and electrons.

Although initially we might perceive this answer as pedantic and adopting a “whig” perspective (in Herbert Butterfield’s phrase) by elevating modern science to a maximum status and showing little willingness for corrections, by categorically rejecting the idea that something we consider fundamental could be wrong. But an approach I consider more useful is that this answer suggests that we have quite possibly reached an interpretation of nature that is good enough and precise enough, which may not be so different from the one held in the future.

I am aware that attempting to predict the future of science falls into no other category than mere speculation, but I consider it an interesting exercise that can help understand the nature of scientific endeavor. Making the distinction that despite the countless number of people throughout history who have already tried to do this very thing, each has taken different degrees of liberties when imagining what would happen. We can discern between those perspectives that allow the imagination to fly without sufficiently considering the true capabilities of nature and, on the other hand, the stance of the man of science. The latter, endowed with a greater understanding of his discipline, from whom we are inclined to expect a higher precision in his reflections on the scientific future.

Following this line of thought and guided by the experiences of those who operate in the realm of scientific creation, we can affirm that although we do not have a complete view of the panorama, we have made significant advances. There are well-founded reasons to support the idea that, although tasks remain to be done, we are eventually approaching a possible stagnation in the field of science at its fundamental levels or even the point where we reach the totality of our potential knowledge.

Perspectives on Scientific Progress

Upon hearing this thesis, reflections are likely to arise on the numerous occasions when it has been thought that the pinnacle of knowledge had been

reached. We can start our journey with the ancient Greeks who, long before the Renaissance, took the physical ideas of Plato and Aristotle as irrefutable truths; for many, everything had already been said [2, 3].

Centuries later, in the 19th century, the perception spread that classical physics already offered a practically complete description of nature, thanks to the contributions of Newton and the development of thermodynamics [4]. Lord Kelvin (William Thomson) is frequently attributed the extreme stance that “there was nothing new to be discovered”, but this phrase is actually apocryphal and is not found in any of his writings¹. What Kelvin did express—in a very different way—was that in the “clear sky” of classical physics only “two small dark clouds” remained, alluding to apparently minor problems that, ironically, ended up originating scientific revolutions.

Needless to say, 19th-century confidence in the completeness of classical physics did not age well; barely into the 20th century, Einstein and other physicists developed the theory of relativity and quantum mechanics. “*These theories eclipsed Newtonian physics and opened vast new vistas for modern physics and other branches of science*” [7, p. 39].

Considering the above, we can strive to identify some pattern suggesting that every time an apparently calm panorama appears, it is asserted that science has reached its end in its current form. However, this perception is constantly challenged by disruptions in scientific thought that force us to create a new understanding.

At first glance, this is a moment where questioning the constant progress of science seems to make no sense; that is, we are not at all in a situation where we have an apparently calm panorama, there are still great problems to which we should try to give a solution, for example: very hot or very cold things, things that move very fast, dark matter and energy. But the idea that science has always advanced and that it now advances faster than ever is a mere illusion as John Horgan exposes [7, p. 42]:

Science has only existed for a few hundred years, and its most spectacular achievements have occurred within the last century.

¹The phrase “there is nothing new to be discovered in physics now; all that remains is more and more precise measurement” is often cited as Kelvin’s, but no textual evidence exists. The idea comes from a more nuanced statement by Albert A. Michelson in 1903 [5]. Kelvin’s genuine declaration on the state of physics appears in his 1900 lecture, where he mentions “two small clouds” in the clear sky of classical physics [6].

Viewed from a historical perspective, the modern era of rapid scientific and technological progress appears not to be a permanent feature of reality, but an aberration, a fluke, a product of a singular convergence of social, intellectual, and political factors.

Accepting the notion that progress is not eternal implies recognizing the limits of what we can know. We can consider the following analogy which is particularly useful to illustrate this point; “*The first explorers, unable to find the edge of the Earth, might well have concluded that it was infinite, but they would have been wrong*”[7, p. 39]. This idea, in turn, provides a starting point for addressing the question of what the ultimate destiny of science would be and how reaching it might possibly not turn out as exciting as we might imagine.

Contrary to what we might think after William Thompson’s disastrous assertion that no one would venture to speculate on the end of physics, renowned scientists emerged raising their doubts about the future of this discipline. I would like to first focus attention on what Richard Feynman said [8]:

-What of the future of this adventure? What will happen ultimately?

-We are going along guessing the laws; how many laws are we going to have to guess? I do not know.

-Some of my colleagues say, well, science will go on. But certainly there will not be perpetual novelty, say for a thousand years. This thing cannot keep going on so that we are always going to discover new laws, new laws, new laws. If we do, it will become boring that there are so many levels one underneath the other. So, it seems to me that the only way that it can happen in the future is, in the first place, that the whole thing becomes known, that all the laws become known; that would mean that after you have enough laws you could compute consequences and they would always agree with experiment, which would be the end of the line, or it might happen that the experiments get harder and harder to make, more and more expensive, so you get 99.9% of the phenomena, but there is always some phenomenon which has just been discovered, which is very hard to measure, and which

disagrees, and as soon as you have the explanation of that one there is always another one, and it gets slower and slower and more and more uninteresting.

—That is another way it may end. But I think it has to end in one way or another.

Beyond the fact that a person so influential for the science of the time is proposing that science is finite, his arguments are quite logical. Analyzing the first of these scenarios, we first undertake the task of seeing how much our understanding of the universe has advanced. Furthermore, at this point, I consider that in order to make our task simpler we must focus more on that part of science that is more concerned with fundamental relationships rather than emergent phenomena, since it is here that we can see most clearly how we have taken giant steps in understanding nature.

If we start from Isaac Newton (so as not to go back so far), we will realize that if we take his axioms we really have a great tool that dictates how the dynamics will be not only of terrestrial bodies but also of celestial ones, such that with a single theory the heavens and the earth are united. This theory, despite being consistent with experience (provided we accept a certain degree of uncertainty in what we measure and predict) in a wide range of problems (we still use it to get to the moon), scientists of the late 19th and early 20th centuries, when putting it to the test in extreme conditions, realized that it was not infallible and a new way of understanding the world was necessary to explain that little bit that escaped Newton, having as a destination the proposition of the theory of relativity and quantum mechanics.

Following this idea historically, we can posit a point where 90% of phenomena were successfully explained by Newton's system, to subsequently (I chose the percentages purely hypothetically solely for the purpose of illustrating the point) with the new emerging theories at the beginning of the 20th century be able to explain 95% of everything that happens. So we have conceived until now a system with bases solid enough and well supported by experience where I am forced to repeat, that although much work remains to be done and several open problems remain, I do not consider that in any future our conception of reality requires a revision from scratch and comes to be branded (in a whig manner) as a naive vision comparable to Aristotelian physics.

Limits of Experimentation

Taking into account Koyré's idea [9], who points out that great scientific revolutions are essentially theoretical revolutions, we can partially blind ourselves regarding a fundamental part of science and say that we can create science in a merely theoretical manner. However, at some point we must put our theories to the test by submitting them to the verdict of nature itself. An illustrative historical example is the description of planetary orbits and the Ptolemaic system of epicycles. Although this system had certain problems, broadly speaking it explained what was observed. However, with the collection of better data and the proposal and confirmation of the Copernican system, theory and practice united, showing the importance of this relationship.

Today, the theoretical part of physics is creating solutions that are mathematically consistent with what we know. An example is string theories or quantum gravity, great candidates for achieving the unification of general relativity with quantum theory. The problem lies in the fact that, despite the incredible beauty and mathematical consistency they present, the link uniting the physical world with theory seems increasingly difficult to find. This difficulty translates into an apparently unbridgeable gap between theoretical predictions and the experimental results we are capable of obtaining.

As [10] indicates: “*Without theorists, experimentalists would have no guidance on what to look for. Without experimentalists, theorists would have no guidance on what to think*”. If experimental science cannot keep pace with theoretical science, we will eventually be condemning science to be stripped of one of its senses, leaving it merely reduced to philosophy.

Furthermore, now more than ever, it seems that there will no longer be great discoveries that we can make with materials available on the market. We have left behind those times when Eratosthenes could measure the curvature of the Earth with a stick, a camel, and the shadow cast by the sun, when Galileo was able to checkmate Aristotle's physics with only pendulums and inclined planes, or when Cavendish estimated the gravitational constant with only a torsion balance. Although the conditions for doing science have improved and individual people or small collectives have achieved incredible things, like Pierre and Marie Curie discovering radium in a shed, Michelson and Morley disproving the existence of ether, or Millikan measuring the charge of the electron with his famous oil drop experiment, or the cloud cham-

ber experiment which is an extremely simple experiment showing the traces of subatomic particles. But it seems that as we advance in time, complexity increases, and although technology has advanced and we have children creating nuclear reactors at home (search for David Hahn), important discoveries seem only reachable in giant machines or in cooperation with a lot of people, whether in initiatives like CERN, LIGO, or the use of a network of observatories to capture images of black holes.

Even when making a large amount of resources available internationally, we are limited by the technology of our time. The most notable example is the LHC, a project that took decades in development. Despite great discoveries like the Higgs boson (one of the most important in the history of physics), it was a bit disappointing for researchers not to find something else, something unexpected, and create new physics. Current physicists' speculation indicates that to find something new with particle collisions, we would need a collider the size of a planetary orbit. CERN researchers, like Harry Cliff [11], suggest that:

If we have found nothing other than the Higgs boson, we may be entering a new era of physics: an era where there are strange features of the universe that we cannot explain; an era where we have hints that we live in a multiverse that lies frustratingly forever beyond our reach; an era where we will never be able to answer the question: “Why is there something rather than nothing?”

Limits of the Human Mind

One of the aspects we must discuss when talking about the limits of scientific progress is the very limitation of the human mind's capacity. I think we can take as a starting point that, in the first instance, for scientific progress to exist, it must be possible for us as humans to make contributions to it, and in order for this to be done, those who wish to solve the great problems posed must first of all be able to understand them and have enough luck and creativity to provide a new approach.

Possibly at some time in our lives we have heard that in basic education we are taught what the wisest men of ancient Greece knew, in intermediate education what the wisest of the Renaissance knew, in upper secondary what the wisest of the 17th century knew, in higher education what the wisest of

the early 20th century knew. Beyond the accuracy in dates and content of this popular saying, we can extract the idea that as higher education is reached, we are able to understand contributions made more recently.

In this era, if we take a physics graduate who, after an accumulated education of around 18 years and an age of 23 years (in standard and ideal conditions), will not be able to understand the current context of physics in all its splendor, that is, with full knowledge of the mathematical and theoretical details that escape popularization, so it is evident that to be able to even have a notion of current physics (and not even of it in its completeness, but only of a somewhat reduced field) will take another amount of years, and after this long journey it can finally be said that they have the minimum bases to make a contribution.

We can make a comparison between physicists now and those of the 16th century when it was not necessary to dedicate a large number of years to master your discipline, and they could even afford the luxury of being polyglots, whereas in our time this is something so difficult if not impossible. So there is the very sure possibility that we reach the point where a number of years is required that even exceeds the amount of time that can be effectively dedicated to the pursuit of knowledge, where ultimately life and the human mind do not even reach to comprehend a small spectrum of human knowledge.

Undoubtedly a part that will worry us in the near future can be seen by alluding to Albert Einstein's famous phrase that said: "***A person who has not made his great contribution to science before the age of 30 will never do so***". While it is true that we cannot take a personal opinion as an absolute truth even if it comes from a person so relevant to the discipline, the truth is that it seems he is not so wrong. Let's take for example a study conducted by Big Think and Barabási [12] where the conclusion is reached that apparently in a large number of scientists the best contributions or at least those that have the most impact are made in the first 15 years of their career, which would seem to indicate that one needs to be young to be creative and contribute something. Examples of this we can take Newton who at the age of 23 had been able to create the foundations of a new physics, or the mathematician Évariste Galois who died at 20, but it was enough for the invention of group theory. Einstein at 26 published his theory of special relativity, Carl Friedrich Gauss published "Disquisitiones Arithmeticae" around his 25 years. We could continue giving examples that satisfy this age restriction; while it is true that there are examples of scientists whose greatest contributions were made outside the range of the first 15 years

of their career, it seems this is not the norm.

Although another consequence is that contributions that were fruitful, in view of their complexity, take us longer to assimilate and recognize. We can see this reflected in the analysis made by Santo Fortunato [13]:

Curiously, the Nobel Prize in Physics is the one that has aged the most: while now the laureates average over 60 years old, this award used to be collected by brilliant young people. The most precocious Nobel is Lawrence Bragg's in Physics, in 1915, when he was 25 years old. And the three youngest are also in Physics; Werner Heisenberg in 1932, Paul Dirac in 1933, and Carl Anderson in 1936 were all 31 years old when they were rewarded.

This point does not contradict the previous one, it only adds the factor of time necessary to receive recognition, which in a certain way can also reflect that inside science, in its most important and fundamental contributions, is suffering a slower deceleration process.

Conclusions

Through a historical analysis, we have observed how theories once considered infallible were replaced by new, more precise and broader interpretations. However, the fundamental question persists: To what extent can we continue this process of discovery and understanding?

The assertion that we have reached a sufficiently good and precise interpretation of nature, although challenging, invites us to consider the possibility that, in general terms, our current theories may not differ drastically from those that will be maintained in the future. This approach, although it may be considered “whig” in its apparent rejection of future fundamental revisions, suggests that we have built foundations solid enough to withstand the passage of time.

However, the limits of experimentation and the increasing complexity of current theories pose significant challenges. The need for more complex experiments suggests that we might be reaching a point where technology and available resources limit our capacity to explore new scientific frontiers.

Furthermore, the question of the limits of the human mind raises concerns about the capacity of individuals to assimilate and contribute to increasingly specialized fields. The historical trend towards significant contributions in

the early stages of a scientific career raises the question of whether science can continue advancing at a similar pace in the future.

After what we have developed, we can share the point of view expressed by [7, p. 36] when he says that

By far the greatest barrier to future progress in pure science is its past success. Researchers have already mapped physical reality, ranging from the micro realm of quarks and electrons to the macro realm of planets, stars, and galaxies.

Also remembering that I do not possess the gift of foreseeing with certainty the exact course of events to come. Although a considerable amount of work remains to be done and various lines of research remain open, I believe that technological progress will open doors to a more promising future. In my perspective, we will reach a point where, although we will not presume to have all the answers resolved, we will find ourselves faced with the possibility that perhaps we cannot answer all the questions, and I do not refer to some of the great questions of our times such as dark matter or energy, but to those questions about the universe that we have not even formulated. I genuinely hope to be wrong (although there are good reasons to believe we will reach that point), and I maintain the hope that the constant intellectual curiosity inherent in our species motivates us to continue exploring and discovering new horizons.

Annex

Below is added a chat John Horgan had with Nobel Prize winner in physics Roger Penrose in the summer of 1989 at Syracuse University. I consider that this chat reflects well the thoughts usually held regarding the idea that science is finite. This was extracted from [7, p. 23-24].

Penrose is an admitted Platonist. Scientists do not invent truth; they discover it. Genuine truths exude a beauty, a rightness, a self-evident quality that gives them the power of revelation. In Penrose's view, superstring theory possessed none of these traits. He admitted that the "suggestion" he formulated in *The Emperor's New Mind* -he admitted it did not yet merit the term theory- was rather ungainly. It might prove wrong, especially in its details. But he was sure it was closer to the truth than superstring theory. In saying this, I asked, was Penrose implying that someday scientists would find the answer and thus end their quest? Unlike some prominent scientists, who seem to equate hesitation with weakness, Penrose actually thinks before he answers, and even while he answers. "I don't think we're close," he said slowly, squinting out his office window, "but that doesn't mean things can't move fast at some point." He pondered a bit more. "I suppose that suggests rather that there is an answer," he continued, "although perhaps that is too pessimistic." This final comment stopped me in my tracks. What is pessimistic, I asked, about a truth seeker thinking that truth is attainable? "Solving mysteries is a wonderful thing," Penrose replied. "And if they were all solved, somehow, it would be rather boring." Then he chuckled, as if surprised by the strangeness of his own words.

Long after leaving Syracuse, I reflected on Penrose's comments. Was it possible that science could come to an end? Could scientists, in effect, learn all there is to know? Could they banish mystery from the universe? I found it hard to imagine a world without science, and not just because my job depended on it. I had become a science writer largely because I considered science (pure science, the pursuit of knowledge for its own sake) to be the noblest and most meaningful of human enterprises. We are here to figure out why we are here. What other purpose is worthy of

us?

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